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Titel

Element Mapping and Biomarker Analyses in an Early Byzantine City (Caricin Grad, Serbia)

Abstract

Soil analyses have a high potential to contribute to the investigation of daily life in ancient settlements. They can help to locate areas of food production, areas of waste disposal, latrines, stables and further functional areas. However, the applicability of these analyses is still restricted by a limited number of studies and a limited knowledge of their validity. In a multi-disciplinary project investigating the daily life in an early byzantine city (Caricin Grad), a multi-element-mapping and biomarker analyses were performed. The study focused on a comparison of the soil data with the data from other disciplines. The Caricin Grad Caricin Grad site in southern Serbia offered excellent conditions for this methodological study. It is supposed to be identical to Iustiniana Prima, an administrative center founded by the emperor Justinian. The period of occupation covered less than 90 years from circa 530 to 615 AD. The site remained undisturbed from later settlement encroachments. Therefore, it allows a rare archaeological 'snapshot' of a short period of very intensive use. By analyses of the amounts of total organic carbon, total phosphorus and further elements (aqua-regia extraction), it was possible to divide different functional areas within the city. Element ratios and biomarkers including faecal steroids were used to get information on the specific use of the functional areas as well as on animal husbandry within the settlement. Data of soil analyses were compared and correlated with data that were obtained by consequent single point measurement and examination of the archaeological remains, 3D photography of the structures as well as archaeobotanical and archaeozoological analyses.